

Pythagoras' Theorem without Matrices?

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Given the Pythagoras' theorem $x^2+y^2=r^2$, one may derive this using 2×2 matrices, i.e. considering a 2×2 matrix which transforms $(r,0)$ column (or $(0,r)$) into (x,y) , One may then transpose the matrix with $(r,0)$ row multiplied by the matrix transposed multiplied by the matrix multiplied by $(r,0)$ column to find that $x^2+y^2=r^2$. This is common knowledge based on a rotation matrix.

In this note, we ask if one may obtain $x^2+y^2=r^2$ without using matrices. We first suggest that r maps into a set of x,y values if one considers moving a radius on a circle from $(0,r)$ to $(r,0)$. Given that r is a single number, each corresponding pair (x,y) must map into this same single number. Thus, one seeks a mapping of two numbers, x,y into one number r . We then consider that one may x or $-x$ and y or $-y$ and suggest that one requires an even power of x and y with no x y mixing (i.e. no x multiplied by y). This leads to the sum of: $x^2 + x^4 + \dots + y^2 + y^4 + \dots$ as a possible solution. If one notes that (x,y) maps into $\{.5(x+y), .5(x-y)\}$ with no information lost and argues for no mixing of x,y , then only x^2+y^2 as a general formula delivers this property. We thus suggest that $x^2+y^2=r^2$ is the way to map (x,y) into r .

It is possible that this approach or one similar has already been presented in the literature due to the interest in Pythagoras' theorem.

Pythagoras' Theorem With Matrices

If one has a radius of a circle, it has a length r which is a single number, but (x,y) projections which represent a pair of numbers. One wishes to map (x,y) into a single number. This may be easily done using a 2×2 matrix which when multiplied by $(r,0)$ column changes it into (x,y) column. Given that a matrix does not look like a single number, one may argue that $\text{number} * I$, where I is the 2×2 identity matrix is equivalent to a single number. One may then take the transpose of the 2×2 matrix multiplied by $(r,0)$ column and multiply it against the same 2×2 matrix (not transposed) and $(r,0)$ column. This yields $r^2=x^2+y^2$ and is associated with rotations.

We consider, however, what one should do if one does wish to introduce matrices.

Pythagoras' Theorem without Matrices

As noted above, a radius length r maps into (x,y) pairs. Given a specific (x,y) pair, $(-x,y)$, $(x,-y)$ and $(-x,-y)$ are also suitable and map into the same r . This seems to imply a mapping formula which uses even powers of x and y . The next question is: Can one mix, (i.e. multiply) x and y terms together in this formula? We suggest that given an (x_1,y_1) corresponding to r_1 that $2r_1$ is linked to $(2x_1,2y_1)$. We generalize this to note that $(x,y)+(x_1,y_1) = (x+x_1, y+y_1)$. In other words, no mixing of x and y occurs and we consider this an essential requirement even when mapping (x,y) into r .

This then leads to the possible solution:

$$X^2 + a_1 x^4 + \dots + y^2 + a_1 y^4 + \dots \quad ((1))$$

Here we consider the same coefficients for x and y . ((1)) is not the Pythagoras' theorem. Certainly at the power 2 level one cannot have mixing because this would mean xy and $(-x,y)$ yields a different value. For power (4), one could have $x^4 + y^4 = r^4$

We next note that given (x,y) , the pair $\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(x+y), \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(x-y) \}$ contain exactly the same information because: $x = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(x+y) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(x-y)$ and $y = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(x+y) - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(x-y)$. One mixes x and y here, but this is fine because this is simply a math transformation. We do not, however, wish to have any x - y mixing in the formula mapping (x,y) to r . In fact, one requires that using $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(x+y)$ and $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(x-y)$ also yields the same result as using x and y .

In other words, the main argument is that mixing x and y linearly should lead to no x multiplied by y terms in the possible formula ((1)) mapping x,y to r . For this to occur, only power 2 may be retained, i.e.

$$\frac{1}{2}(x+y)^2 + \frac{1}{2}(x-y)^2 = x^2 + y^2 \text{ which should equal } r^2 \text{ ((2))}$$

((2)) is Pythagoras' theorem.

This approach does inherently seem to use the idea of matrices as the vector $\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(x+y), \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(x-y) \}$ may be obtained from (x,y) using a 2×2 matrix. If one uses a 2×2 matrix to transform (x,y) into $\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(x+y), \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(x-y) \}$, then there is no reason not to use one to transform $(r,0)$ into (x,y) and solve the problem using matrices. The fact that one uses 2×2 matrices already suggests a power (2) form. Explicitly, however, matrices are not used above.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that one may obtain Pythagoras' theorem without using matrices. The idea is to map (x,y) into r , but $(x,-y)$, $(-x,y)$ and $(-x,-y)$ are just as suitable so we suggest a formula which has even powers of x and y and the further condition that this formula does not mix x and y values, i.e. does not have x even power multiplied by y even power anywhere. We then note that the information in (x,y) is identical to that in $\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(x+y), \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(x-y) \}$. This involves x,y mixing, but only as a math transformation. x and y must not be mixed if one uses this new pair in a general formula instead of x and y . Originally if one has x and y to even powers, one may have 2,4, 6 etc. If $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(x+y)$ and $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(x-y)$ may be substituted for x and y and one wishes no x - y mixing, then one may only have power 2, i.e. $x^2 + y^2 = r^2$.